

Note:

This document contains a lay summary of the article “Data sharing ethics toolkit: The Human Cell Atlas” by Kirby et al. Nature Communications (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-54300-3>. Please use this citation when referring to this work. Translation of this lay summary to other languages can be found at <https://zenodo.org/communities/hcaewg/>

Data sharing ethics toolkit: The Human Cell Atlas

Authors

Emily Kirby (1), Alexander Bernier (1), Roderic Guigó (2), Barbara Wold (3), Fabiana Arzuaga (4), Mayumi Kusunose (5), Ma'n Zawati (1), Bartha M. Knoppers (1).

- (1) Centre of Genomics and Policy, School of Biomedical Sciences, Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, McGill University, 740 Dr. Penfield, Suite 5200, Montreal, QC, Canada
- (2) Bioinformatics and Genomics, Center for Genomic Regulation (CRG), The Barcelona Institute for Science and Technology (BIST), Dr. Aiguader 88, 08003 Barcelona, Catalonia Universitat Pompeu Fabra (UPF), Barcelona, Catalonia
- (3) Division of Biology and Biological Engineering, California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, CA, 91125, USA
- (4) Interministerial Commission on Advanced Therapies
Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation -Argentina
Godoy Cruz 2320. 4th Floor, Ciudad Autónoma de Buenos Aires, Argentina
- (5) IMS RIKEN Center for Integrative Medical Sciences
1-7-22 Suehiro-cho, Tsurumi-ku, Yokohama City, Kanagawa, 230-0045, Japan

The correspondence in English related to this article can be submitted to Emily Kirby (emily.kirby@mail.mcgill.ca).

Summary**What is the Human Cell Atlas?**

The Human Cell Atlas (HCA) research initiative is mapping every cell type in the human body. This will transform our understanding of biology and disease, and revolutionise the way illnesses are diagnosed and treated.

Every living thing is made up of cells, which are the tiny building blocks of the body. Using cutting edge technology, the Human Cell Atlas is creating a detailed map of all our cells and what they do.

There are about 37 trillion cells in the human body and each one has its own specialised job. For example some cells join together to create organs like the brain or lungs or liver, or develop into blood cells that circulate around the body. Understanding our cells is vital to understanding how

the human body works and what goes wrong in disease, but we still don't even know how many different types of cell there are.

The HCA is creating a 3-dimensional map of all human cells. Once this is made, researchers will be able to zoom into a map of the body like a 'Google map', zooming into organs, then into tissues, then cells - to understand every human cell type, across time from development to old age.

This map will be freely available across the world, helping scientists understand biology and diseases. HCA research is already providing insights, including into cancer, heart and lung diseases, Covid-19, cystic fibrosis and other diseases. The Atlas will lead to new ways of diagnosing and treating illness, and will transform future healthcare.

What is complex about the ethical and legal aspects of the Human Cell Atlas?

The HCA itself does not collect or analyse the biological tissue samples and no samples are shared with the HCA (only data). Rather, the HCA relies on a large community of scientists and research participants, around the world, who choose to submit data related to tissue samples they have collected as part of their local work.

This means that data that is contributed to the HCA are collected in different countries, under different rules (laws, regulations, institutional policies). Even within a single country, the rules can be different depending on the type of biological tissue sampled and the context in which it was taken. For example, there may be specific legal and ethical requirements that apply depending on whether samples are collected from adult or pediatric participants, living vs. deceased individuals, or in a clinical context vs. a research context, etc.

Different countries also have different rules on the protection and privacy of personal data, which can include certain types of research data. This has an impact on how data associated with these samples can be transferred to the HCA and made accessible to researchers using the Human Cell Atlas.

Tools were developed by the Human Cell Atlas Ethics Working Group

From a legal and ethical perspective, creating a large-scale research infrastructure like the HCA involves a complicated legal and ethical framework. To look at these issues, the HCA set up an Ethics Working Group (EWG), which has been working to build a solid foundation to address the complexities of data collection and sharing as part of atlas development. Documentation was developed by the HCA EWG to propose ways to meet local and international research and data protection rules.

The HCA ethics toolkit is publicly available online at: www.humancellatlas.org/ethics Different tools were developed to assist HCA stakeholders at various points in the data lifecycle (collection, storage and sharing). These include, for example:

- Consent tools and consent form templates;
- Documents explaining the HCA to local research team and their ethics review committees (i.e. committees which review the scientific validity of research and ensure the protection of research participants at the local site where research is done)

- Documents to help researchers share tissue samples and associated data.

Several of these tools can be used by researchers to customize them to specific situations, such as populations (e.g. pediatric) or situations (e.g. clinical, research, tissue donation, etc.).

We hope that the EWG's work, particularly the models proposed in the ethics toolkit, will help future international research efforts in developing similar approaches. We suggest that these approaches need to consider the local requirements of contributing scientists (e.g. laws, policies). They should also establish common methods for data collection and sharing (like template consent language) to allow the data collected in different regions and contexts to be shared for the creation of a larger research resources like the HCA. In time, we would like the tools to evolve as feedback is received from the community of researchers and other stakeholders contributing to and using the atlas.